

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№12

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

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Elektron nashr. 2025-yil, dekabr.

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA DAVRIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI LIKVIDLILIK XAVFINI BOSHQARISHI.....	44
Baxromov Nodirjon Muxammadamin o'g'li	
TURIZM XIZMATLAR BOZORI ISTE'MOLCHILARINI SEGMENTLASH USULI ASOSIDA DIVERSIFIKATSIYA KONSEPSIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH.....	48
Maxmudova Aziza Pirmamatovna	
"INNOVATSION AGROTEKNOLOGIYALAR VA "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT" TAMOIYILLARI ASOSIDA G'ALLA YETISHTIRISH BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	53
Turayeva Gulizahro	
АНАЛИЗ ЦЕНОБРАЗОВАНИЯ НА ЗЕРНОВЫЕ ПРОДУКТЫ ПО ДАННЫМ МАРКЕТИНГОВЫМ ИСЛЕДОВАНИЯМ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ НАМАНГАНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ).....	57
Бахриддинов Жаҳонгирбек Равшанжон ўғли	
KICHIK BIZNES RIVOJINI TA'MINLASHDA BOZOR INFRATUZILMALARINING AHAMIYATI.....	62
G'aniyev Botir Baxtiyorovich, Zakirova Gulnora Mirzaliyevna	
KICHIK SANOAT ZONALARI FAOLIYATINI SAMARALI BOSHQARISH METODOLOGIYASI VA YO'LLARI.....	67
Shodmonqulov Kamoliddin Murodillaevich	
INNOVATION FAOLIYAT XARAJATLARINING BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI VA AUDITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	73
Mustafoyev Akbar Mustafo o'g'li	
MAHSULOT DIVERSIFIKATSIYASI VA LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ASOSIDA EKSPORT POTENSIALINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	78
Maxkamov Ibrayim, Jo'raboyeva Shohida Kamoliddin qizi	
REKLAMA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI MARKETING STRATEGIYALARI ROLI.....	83
Abdusalilova Laylo To'xtasinovna, Raxmonqulova Shahrizoda	
SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOTDA YOPIQ SIKL NAZARIYASINING ROLI.....	87
Sodikov Zokir Rustamovich	
YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHDA MOLIYAVIY RAG'BATLAR VA ULARNING NATIJALARI.....	92
Axmadjonova Gulmira Xabibulla qizi	
MAMLAKAT IQTISODIYOTI RIVOJLANISHIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNING ROLI.....	97
G'aniyev Baydulla Toshmurodovich	
АНАЛИЗ ПОДХОДОВ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНЫХ БАНКОВ К РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЮ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ БАНКОВСКИХ ПРОДУКТОВ: СРАВНЕНИЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ ПРАКТИКИ.....	101
Даулетиярова Шахло	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ЦЕННЫХ БУМАГ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	109
Кадилова Хадича Тураевна	
XORIJ MAMLAKATLARINING IQTISODIYOTNI UGLERODSIZLASHTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI: O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN TAKLIFLAR.....	115
D.X. Pulatov, F.E.Shamsiyev	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISLOM MOLIYASI: MUAMMOLAR VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	125
Sattorov Ixtiyor Ochilovich, Karimov Shohruh Yo'ldoshali o'g'li	
HISOB SIYOSATI TARKIBIY TUZILISHI MASALALARI.....	133
Botirova Raximaxon Abdujabbarovna	
QURILISHDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNING MOLIYAVIY TAHLILI.....	136
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	

KICHIK SANOAT ZONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI AHOLI TURMUSH FAROVONLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	144
<i>Axmedov Oybek Turgunpulatovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORI PORTFELI TAHLILI.....	149
<i>Madraximov Ilxom Kamilovich</i>	
FOYDA SOLIG'INING O'ZIGA XOS MUAMMOLI JIHATLARI.....	154
<i>Zaripov Xusan Baxodirovich</i>	
AGRAR SEKTORNI INNOVATSION MODERNIZATSIYA QILISHDA INVESTITSIYA OQIMLARINI BOSHQARISH MODELLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	159
<i>Xamrayev Quvvat Iskandarovich</i>	
OLIY TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA MARKETING TADQIQODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	163
<i>Jalilov Jamshid G'anjionovich, Safarov Zavqiddin Zokir o'g'li</i>	
MINTAQA SANOAT TARMOG'I RIVOJLANISHINING IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI.....	168
<i>Xayitboev Abror Quvondiqovich</i>	
РОЛЬ СМЕШАННОГО ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ (BLENDED FINANCE) В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ КОММУНАЛЬНЫХ УСЛУГ: УРОКИ РАЗВИВАЮЩИХСЯ СТРАН.....	174
<i>Гулмаматова Дурдона Шерали кизи</i>	
KORXONALARDA STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV.....	180
<i>Musayeva Dilnoza Dilshatovna</i>	
BANK TIZIMIDA MARKETING AHAMIYATI VA BANK MARKETINGI.....	184
<i>Usubjonov Zaxriddin Vasliddin o'g'li</i>	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN XORJIY KREDIT MABLAG'LARINI JALB KILISH HUQUQIY JIHATLARI.....	189
<i>Qulliyev Anvar Zayniddinovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARINI TRANSFORMATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA CHAKANA XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	194
<i>Alimov Umid O'ktambayevich</i>	
MAHSULOTLARNING RAQAMLI PASPORTI TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH OMILLARI VA TO'SIQLARI.....	200
<i>Avloqulova Sadoqat Sobirjon qizi</i>	
KORXONALARDA FOYDA VA ZARARLARNI TAHLIL QILISHDA INNOVATSION METODLAR AHAMIYATI.....	207
<i>Ernazarov Ortiq Eshnazarovich, Farog'at Xo'jabekova</i>	
ВЛИЯНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА НА ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ БЛАГОСОСТОЯНИЕ, А ТАКЖЕ НОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ДОХОДОВ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ.....	212
<i>Останов Эгамберди</i>	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA INNOVASION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI INTEGRATSIYALASH: MOHIYATI VA RIVOJLANISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	218
<i>Xakimova Xulkar Xamidovna</i>	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON VA XORAZM OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATINING IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI HAMDA UNI YANADA RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	224
<i>Tleuov Niyetulla Raxmanovich</i>	
OILAVIY KORXONALARNING IQTISODIY TIZIMDAGI O'RNI.....	230
<i>Shadiyeva Gulnora Mardiyevna, Rustamova Zarina Rustamovna</i>	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA O'ZBEKISTON OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINI MODELLASHTIRISH VA BOSHQARISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	234
<i>Sadikov Shoxrux Shuxratovich</i>	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASI KORXONALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI XIZMATLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	238
<i>Asenbaeva Aydaygul Edenbaevna</i>	
BARQARORLIK VA YASHIL MENEJMENT: ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR VA AMALIY AHAMIYATI.....	242
<i>Djalilova Dilbar Abdikarim qizi</i>	

HUDUDLARNING IQTISODIY SALOHİYATINI INNAVATSION-INVESTITSION BOSHQARISH STRATEGIYASI VA MEXANIZMI (XORAZM VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	247
Maqsudova Malohatxon Maqsudovna, Yaxshimuratov Maqsadbek Narimon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI DAVLAT BUDJETINI 2026-YILGI SOLIQ SIYOSATINING TAHLILI VA XALQARO SOLISHTIRMA YONDASHUVI	251
Abdullayev Zafarbek Safibullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON MINTAQALARIDA AYOLLAR TADBIRKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILLARI.....	256
Mamataliyeva Dilnoza Raxmonovna	
TRANSFORMATSIYALASHUV SHAROITIDA INVESTITSİYALAR SHAKLLANISHI VA ULARNI SAMARALI BOSHQARISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	259
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SAVDO TASHKILOTLARINING FAOLIYATI VA RIVOJLANISH HOLATI.....	264
B. Sulaymonov	
NAMANGAN VILOYATIDA "YASHIL IQTISODIYOT" MODELIGA O'TISH JARAYONIDA KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING IQTISODIY FAOLLIGI.....	270
Xonto'rayev Obbosxon Kamolxon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	274
Xoshimov Pazliddin Zuxurovich	
KICHIK BIZNES ORQALI ISH O'RINLARINI YARATISH STRATEGIYALARI: NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA.....	278
Ergasheva Nigora Abdigapparovna	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG'INING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	283
Quryozov Sardorbek Sharifboevich	
РАЗРАБОТКА И ПРИОРИТИЗАЦИЯ КЛЮЧЕВЫХ ИНДИКАТОРОВ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ДЛЯ ОБЩЕНАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПАНЕЛИ МОНИТОРИНГА ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ БОЛЬНИЦ: ЭКСПЕРТНАЯ ОЦЕНКА СО СТОРОНЫ РУКОВОДИТЕЛЕЙ МЕДУЧРЕЖДЕНИЙ	290
Шухратов Мамуржон Шухрат угли	
MAHALLIY DAVLAT HOKIMIYAT ORGANLARINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA BOSHQARISHGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR	297
Nurmurodov Zafarjon Nurmurod o'g'li	
BANK TIZIMINING BARQAROR MOLIVAVIY RIVOJLANISHINI TA'MINLASH VOSITALARI	303
Sadikov Iskandar Gayratovich	
ЗЕЛЕНОЕ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЕ В ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА.....	308
Халиков С. Х.	
HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA KICHIK BIZNESNI ROLI VA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH CHORALARI.....	313
Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich	
ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЙ ПРОЦЕСС СТАНОВЛЕНИЯ ФАРМАЦЕВТИЧЕСКОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ.....	317
Мажидова Фарангиз Фуркатзода	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDAGI TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	321
Isakov Oybek Jamoliddinovich	
NORASMIY KOOPERATSIYA MUNOSABATLARINING FERMER XO'JALIKLARI YETISHTIRGAN MAHSULOT MIQDORIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH.....	325
Ismoilov Azamat	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARIDA FOIZ RISKINI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTI.....	332
Seitnazarov Daniyar Baxadirovich	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA SUT VA SUT MAHSULOTLARINI QAYTA ISHLOVCHI KORXONALAR FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	341
Normuradov Nurbek Sunatilloevich	
"AYOL RAHBARLAR: RAHBARLIK SALOHİYATI VA ISH JOYIDA TENGLIK" FRANSIYA DAVLATI TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA	346
Abduraxmonova Feruzabonu	

QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDAGI KLASTERLARNING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH.....	352
Dildora Yuldasheva	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING DEPOZIT BAZASINING YETARLILIGINI TA'MINLASH YO'LLARI	359
I.J. Isakov	
OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISH VA IQTISODIY DIAGNOSTIKA O'TKAZISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI.....	363
Xo'jaxonov Ma'rufxon Xamidxonovich, Axmedov Oybek Turg'unpulatovich	
INKLYUZIV TA'LIMNI MOLIYAVIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHDAGI MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI YECHISH YO'LLARI.....	369
Egamberdiyeva Dilorom Botir qizi, Pulatova Moxira Baxtiyorovna	
“KREATIV IQTISODIYOT” HAMDA “TURIZM” TUSHUNCHALARINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	374
Abdurasulov Shovqiddin Erkin o'g'li	
THE STRATEGIC ROLE OF THE INDUSTRIAL SECTOR IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY AND DEVELOPMENT FACTORS.....	380
Rakhimov Bakhromjon Ibroximovich	
INVESTITSIYALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI.....	386
Ismailov Dilshod Anvarjonovich	
GLOBAL INCOME INEQUALITY IN 2024: CAUSES, PATTERNS, AND CONSEQUENCES.....	393
Ilxomjonov Jaxongir Alisher o'g'li	
ТОРГОВЫЕ ОТНОШЕНИЯ В СВОБОДНО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ЗОНАХ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ	401
Шарифходжаев Шавкат Окилович, Ачилова Ширин Шавкат кизи	
O'ZBEKISTON KON-METALLURGIYA SANOATI: RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI VA HOZIRGI HOLATI	407
Ergashov Botirjon Ergashovich	
PENSIYA JAMG'ARMASIDA DAVLAT BUDJETI TRANSFERTLARI ULUSHI HAMDA UNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI.....	415
Sherjonov Doniyor Saparbayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT KORXONALARINI QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR BOZORIDAN FOYDALANIB MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI.....	419
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG'I BO'YICHA FIRIBGARLIKLAR: MEXANIZMLARI, SABABLARI VA ULARNI OLDINI OLISH YO'LLARI.....	425
Eshkarayev Bobir Chariyevich	
TOG' VA TOG'OLDI HUDUDLARIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	431
Abdulxayeva Gulshan Maxmudovna	
TURIZM SOHASINING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI (SAMARQAND VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	435
Xalimov Shaxboz Xalimovich	
SANOATDA IQTISODIY MOLIYAVIY HISSOBOTLAR XALQARO STANDARTLARINI RAQOBATBARDOSH KORPORATIV STRATEGIYALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA QO'LLASH.....	442
Turaboev Ibroxim Ismoil o'g'li	
ФОНДИРОВАНИЕ И СТРАХОВАНИЕ В СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ РИСКАМИ АПК: СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ	447
Дурманов Акмал Шаймарданович	
PAHTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARI RIVOJLANISHINING STATISTIK KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILI	456
Atajanova Guli Maxsudbekovna	
JAHON MOLIYAVIY BOZORLARI BARQARORLIGIGA GLOBAL IQTISODIY INQIROZLAR VA GEOSIYOSIY OMILLARNING TA'SIRI HAMDA ULARNI BOSHQARISH STRATEGIYALARI	462
Abdurazakova Nargiza Rixsibayevna	

QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARINI ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA BOSHQARUV QARORLARINING IQTISODIY TAHLILI.....	467
Mamadiyarov Dilshad Uralovich	
PAXTA TOZALASH KORXONALARINING TARKIBIY BO'LINMALARIDA MOLIVAVIY BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	474
Murodov Orif Jumayevich, G'ulomov Xaydarbek Ilyos o'g'li	
BARQAROR KELAJAK SARI: MAMLAKATDA EKOLOGIK XAVFSIZLIKNI MUSTAHKAMLASH	482
Abdullaev Shavkatjon Maxmudillaevich	
ZAMONAVIY IQTISODIY SHAROITLARDA KORXONALARNING MOLIVAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH	487
Abdulakimova Moxina Farxod qizi	
UMUMIY OVQATLANISH SHAHOBCHALARINING FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	493
Amiriddinova Muslima Zayniddin qizi	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA MIJOZLAR EHTIYOJINI O'RGANISH VA XIZMAT SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI	498
Babayeva Lola Ibragimovna	
MINTAQADA TARIXIY VA MADANIY TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARINI KENGAYTIRISHDA DAVLAT HAMDA XUSUSIY SHERIKCHILIK TIZIMIDAN FOYDALANISH	504
Xusanov Chari Kadirovich	
PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	509
Botirova Xulkar Olimjonovna	
THE IMPACT OF AGRICULTURAL CLUSTERS ON FOOD SECURITY AND MACROECONOMIC STABILITY	514
Sherkulov Shohruh Erkin ugli	
OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA ISSIQXONA IQTISODIYOTINI O'RNI VA NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLAR	520
Otavullaev Sukhrob Sa'dullo o'g'li	
IJTIMOY AHAMIYATI YUQORI LOYIHALARNI DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIGI ASOSIDA BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	524
Taspanova Ayzada Kenjebayevna	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARIDA RAQOBAT STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	529
Sharopova Nafosat Radjabovna, Jamolova Aziza	
TIKUV-TRIKOTAJ KORXONALARIDA ISTE'MOLCHILARNING XULQ-ATVORINI O'RGANISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	537
Sultonova Zulxumor, Bobojonov Baxrombek Ro'zimovich	
INTERNATIONAL TRADE BETWEEN INTEGRATION AND ISOLATION: INNOVATION AND UNCERTAINTY IN A FRAGMENTING GLOBAL ECONOMY.....	542
Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI QO'NG'IROT TUMANIDA SIGIRLAR BOSH SONINING PROGNOZ KO'RSATKICHLARI	548
Sabit Gabbarov	
TO'QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORTINI OSHIRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	552
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna, Xo'janova Husnora	
O'ZBEKISTONDA IQTISODIY O'SISH SIFAT OMILLARINING TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	558
Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich	
ОБЩАЯ КОНЦЕПЦИЯ СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РЕСУРСОВ.....	567
Зайналов Джахонгир Расулович	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКОВ КАПИТАЛОВ	571
Хотамкулова Мадина Санжар кизи, Зайналов Джахонгир Расулович	

IPOTEKA KREDITI MEKANIZMLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH BO'YICHA AMALIY ISHLAR TAHLILI	576
A'zamxo'jayeva Nihola Sulaymon qizi	
KORXONALARDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI	581
Abdurashidova Nigora Alisherovna, Abduqodirova Donoxon	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI VA MEZONLARI.....	588
Jumanov Ruslanbek Bobojanovich	
O'ZBEKISTONIDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASI VA UNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI	592
Rasulev Alisher Fayziyevich, Qodirov Asliddinxo'ja Mahammadjon o'g'li	
STUDY OF THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF GREEN BONDS, ECOLOGICAL LOANS, AND GREEN INVESTMENT FUNDS, AS WELL AS THEIR IMPORTANCE IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM.....	595
Avazov Azizbek Ashurali o'g'li	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK TERMINOLOGIYASINING ILMIY-TAHLILII TALQINI.....	603
Aripov Oybek Abdullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA MEHNAT BOZORINING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASI VA UNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI.....	608
Rasulev Alisher Fayziyevich, Qodirov Asliddinxo'ja Mahammadjon o'g'li	
FERMER XO'JALIKLARIDA INVESTITSION JARAYONLARNI TASHKIL ETISH VA OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	611
Kdirbaev Amir Marat uli	
ITALIYA VA YAPONIYADA DAVLAT QARZINING UZOQ MUDDATLI BARQARORLIGI: FISKAL QOIDALAR VA QARZ BOSHQARUVI STRATEGIYALARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI.....	614
Abdurahimov Abror Zafarovich, L.M. Tashpulatova	
ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ: ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ПЕРСОНАЛИЗАЦИИ, ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ	621
Камалова Малика Низамовна, Очилов Акрам Одилович	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNING ISHSIZLIK DARAJASIGA TA'SIRINI IFODALOVCHI ASOSIY OMILLAR.....	626
Raxmonov Bekzod Sharibjon o'g'li	
GLOBAL XAVFLARNING KESKINLASHUVI SHAROITIDA QAYTA SUG'URTANI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	631
Norov Zarif Shamsiddinovich	
INNOVATSION SUG'URTA XIZMATLARINI JORIY ETISH ORQALI IXTIYORIY SUG'URTA XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	638
Xayitov Nodirjon Uzokovich	
VOSITACHILIK XIZMATLARINI KO'RSATUVCHI SUBYEKTLAR AUDITI SIFAT NAZORATI.....	652
O.Q. Qo'shmatov	
AUDITORLIK XULOSASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MATEMATIK MODELLARDAN FOYDALANISH MASALALARI	657
I.Qo'ziyev, F.Ochilov	
MAJBURIYATLAR HISOBINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	664
Ochilov Farxodjon Shavkatjon o'g'li	
ВОПРОСЫ РЕОРГАНИЗАЦИИ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В СЕЛЬКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ	669
Розиков Жалил Жалолович	
TOVAR-MODDIY ZAXIRALAR AUDITINI O'TKAZISH TARTIBI.....	678
M.Xayitboyev	
USTAV KAPITAL HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	683
Inomjon Sherimbetov	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA KOOPERATIVLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	688
Mirzayev Musurmon Umidullayevich, Ziyadullayev Ilhom Narkobilovich	

EKSPORT BOZORLARINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHDA MOLIYAVIY RAG‘BATLARNING ROLI	694
Galiyev Tohir Fazliddinovich	
ZAMONAVIY LOGISTIKA TIZIMIDA MARKETING STARTEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	700
Abduqodirova Umida G‘ayrat qizi	
QASHQADARYO URBANIZATSIYALASHGAN HUDUDLARIDA AGLOMERATSIYA JARAYONLARIGA TA‘SIR KO‘RSATUVCHI OMILLAR	706
Nazarova Feruza Usmonovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN ALOQA KORXONALARINI KREDITLASHNING ZARURLIGI HAMDA IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	713
Shaymatov Mansur Jo‘rabaevich	
MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLARI ASOSIDA MOLIYAVIY AKTIVLARNI TAN OLISH	720
Odiljonova Oybachin Fayzullo qizi	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA INNOVATSION TRANSFORMATSIYA BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH	724
Sanetullaev Aybek Esbosinovich	
XALQARO AVTOMOBIL ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KOMPANIYALARNING RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI	728
Xidoyatov Mirsaid Mirmuhsomovich	
ENSURING THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: STRATEGIES FOR RESILIENCE IN AN ERA OF DECLINING RESOURCES AND RISING EXPECTATIONS.....	734
Inomiddin Imomov	
“YASHIL” TEXNOLOGIYALARNI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA INTEGRATSIYA QILISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	744
Miraxmedova Maftuna Ibragimovna	
ИНТЕГРАЛЬНЫЙ ПОДХОД К ОЦЕНКЕ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	751
Алиева Эльнара Аметовна	
AHOLI DAROMADLARI VA ULARNING SHAKLLANISH MANBALARI.....	756
So‘fiyeva Xusniya Soxibjonovna	
НАУЧНО-МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЮ И РАЗВИТИЮ ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	760
Назарова Гулчехра Нурмуханбетовна	
СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПОДХОДОВ ПО ОЦЕНКЕ ЭКСПЛУАТАЦИОННОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ МАЛОМОЩНЫХ СЕТЕВЫХ ФОТОЭЛЕКТРИЧЕСКИХ СТАНЦИЙ	766
А.Р. Кудратов	
IJTIMOYIY XIZMATLAR KO‘RSATISH JARAYONIDA TASHKILIY VA IQTISODIY MUNOSABATLAR	775
Berdiyeva Nafisa Qahramonovna	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA INNOVATSION BIZNESNI BOSHQARISH VA YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ORQALI SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH	780
Mamadiyarov Dilshad Uralovich, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o‘g‘li	
GRUZIYA TAJRIBASIDA BARQAROR TURIZMNI TA‘MINLASHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARI VA ULARNING O‘ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA QO‘LLANILISHI.....	786
Suyunova Dilnoza Mexridin qizi	
INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNING MINTAQADA XIZMAT KO‘RSATISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDAGI XUSUSIYATLARI	790
Fayziyeva Shirin Shodmonovna	
QORAQALPOG‘ISTON HUDUDIDA ETNOGRAFIK TURIZM KLASTERINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY OMILLARI	795
Kunnazarova Orazxan	
MAMALAKATIMIZ IMPORTI VA EKSPORTIDA KICHIK BIZNESNING ULUSHI	798
Jo‘rayev Ilhomjon Kamolidinovich	
YEVROOBLIGATSIYA VA UNING AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARI TOMONIDAN EMISSIYASI	807
Avezov Ibrohim Ilxomovich	

IQTISODIYOTDAGI INNOVATSION O'ZGARISHLAR SHAROITIDA TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARIDA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI BOSHQARISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	808
<i>Xonkeldiyeva Komilaxon Ravshanjon qizi</i>	
SPORT ANJOMLARI SANOATIDA INNOVATSION JARAYONLARNI TIZIMLASHTIRISH MODELING ZARURATI.....	813
<i>Xamraqulov Ixtiyor Baxtiyorovich</i>	
GREEN MARKETING STRATEGIES AND THE APPLICATION OF NEUROMARKETING METHODS IN THEIR DEVELOPMENT.....	819
<i>Samadov Asqar Nishonovich, Latipova Go'zal</i>	
OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATIDA KICHIK KORXONALAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	825
<i>Mavlanova Barchinoy Shonazar qizi</i>	
BARQAROR IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDA INVESTITSİYALAR AHAMIYATINING EMPERIK TAHLILI	831
<i>Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Najmiddinov Yahyo Fazliddin o'g'li</i>	
YASHIL TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MEHMONXONALAR ROLI: MUAMMOLAR VA IMKONIYATLAR.....	840
<i>Raxmonova Nigina Anvarovna</i>	
IJTIMOY SIYOSAT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI: O'ZBEKISTONNING AMALIY YONDASHUVI VA RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	844
<i>Bafoyev Farrux Jo'raqulovich</i>	
AHOLI IJTIMOY HIMOYASINI KUCHAYTIRISH MUAMMOLARI	852
<i>Ulashev Xubbim Askarovich</i>	
YASHIL TA'LIM RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI: YAPONIYA MISOLIDA	856
<i>Raxshona Nabibullayeva</i>	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA ELEKTRON SAVDONING MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA TA'SIRI.....	861
<i>Mo'minov Yahyobek Shokirjon o'g'li</i>	
TUROPERATORLIK FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI.....	865
<i>Toshev Akmal Salimovich</i>	
TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ORQALI MINTAQADA AHOLI DAROMADLARINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	874
<i>Quldasheva Maftuna Musurmon qizi</i>	
ФАКТОРЫ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ.....	878
<i>Алиева Эльнара Аметовна, Рахматхонов Саидодилхон Расулхон угли</i>	
МЕХАНИЗМЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ В СТРАНАХ С РАЗВИВАЮЩЕЙСЯ ЭКОНОМИКОЙ: РОЛЬ ESG-ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ, ДИНАМИКА РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И МАЛАЙЗИИ.....	884
<i>Нарзуллаева Мехрангиз Акобировна</i>	
DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLAR SAVDOSIDA QIYMAT ZANJIRI TAHLILI: IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH OMILLARI.....	893
<i>Maftuna Ermatova Arslonbek qizi</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON VA TURKMANISTON O'RTASIDAGI SAVDO AYLANMASI TAHLILI	899
<i>Voxidova Mehri Xasanovna</i>	
GLOBAL KOMPANIYALARDA RAQAMLI MENEJMENTNING SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI	905
<i>Axmedov Sardor Shuxrat o'g'li</i>	
IQLIM O'ZGARISHLARI VA GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA EKOLOGIK-HUQUQIY TA'LIMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	912
<i>Jumanazar Xolmuminov</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING JAHON TAJRIBASI	916
<i>Kalandarova Elnura Muzaffar qizi</i>	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA HUDUDLARNING INVESTITSIYAVIY JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	921
<i>Rahmatullayev Bobir Chorshamiyevich</i>	

FINANCING WATER RESILIENCE: A FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS OF SOVEREIGN BLUE BOND ISSUANCE IN UZBEKISTAN.....	926
Yakubov Jakhongir	
УКРЕПЛЕНИЕ ПАРТНЁРСТВО И СОЗДАНИЕ ЕДИНСТВЕННОГО ЭНЕРГОРЫНКА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	929
Каримова Нуржахон Олим кизи	
ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ ЗРЕЛОСТЬ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ КАК ФАКТОР РОСТА ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ: МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ КОМПЛЕКСНОЙ МОДЕЛИ.....	935
Алиева Эльнара Аметовна, Табаков Евгений Сергеевич	
"BUDJET JARAYONLARIDA XAVFLARNI ANIQLASH VA BAHOLASH: ICHKI AUDIT YONDASHUVLARI".....	941
Abdujalilova Dilnoz Abdusattorovna, Nishonxo'djaev Bekzod Baxodir o'g'li	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA DAVLATNING ROLI.....	947
Raximov Baxromjon Ibroximovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SUT SEKTORINING QIYMAT ZANJIRINI SANOATLASHTIRISH MUAMMOLARI.....	951
Urazov Jamshidjon Sa'dullayevich	
STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBIDA XARAJATLAR HISOBI VA KALKULYATSIYA TIZIMLARINING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	955
Hamroyeva Zuhra Amiral qizi	
АНАЛИЗ И ОЦЕНКА ТЕКУЩЕГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ФИНАНСОВОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНЕ.....	961
Ариф Мустафаев	
ФАКТОРЫ ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ДОХОДОВ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В УСЛОВИЯХ РЫНОЧНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ.....	968
Ишонкулова Феруза Асатовна	
O'ZBEKISTONNING INVESTITSION HUQUQIY SIYOSATIDA GLOBAL REYTINGLARNING NORMATIV-HUQUQIY ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	974
Gavhar Bekmurodova Adham qizi	
XALQARO MOLIYA BOZORIDA KREDIT RISKINI BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY USULLARI VA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI.....	981
Ochilova Xusniya Olim qizi, Yuldasheva Umida Asanaliyevna	
JAHONDA BRONLASH TIZIMLARINING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARINING EVOLYUTSIYASI.....	987
Ismatillaeva Sitara Sayfidin qizi	
MILLIY IQTISODIYOT INNOVATSION SALOHİYATIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHDA JAHON TAJRIBALARI.....	994
Samadqulov Muhammadjon Islom o'g'li	
HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISHDA SOLIQ IMTIYOZLARINING AHOLI DAROMADLAR DINAMIKASIGA TA'SIRI.....	998
Olimjon Fattoyev G'ayrat o'g'li	
OLIV TA'LIM MUASSASALARINING ZAMONAVIY SHAROITLARDI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGI: NAZARIY JIHATLARI VA AMALIY BOSHQARUV STRATEGIYALARI.....	1002
Adizov Bobir Baxtiyrovich	
ZAMONAVIY SHAROITDA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI RISKLARINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	1005
Sirojiddinov Kamoliddin Ikromiddinovich, Nasritdinov Bekzod Xusnutdinovich	
NAMANGAN VILOYATIDA QURILISH KLASTERNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ASOSIY OMILLARI VA ISTIQBOLLI MANBALARI.....	1011
Abduraxmanov Muxtorali Abduvoxidovich	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	1016
Авезова Шахноза Махмуджановна	
MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIKNI OSHIRISHGA TA'SIR KO'RSATADIGAN OMILLAR.....	1022
Obilov Mirkomil Rashidovich	

“O‘ZBEKISTONDA TURIZMNING MADANIY IDENTIKLIKA TA’SIRI: SOTSILOGIK TAHLIL”	1028
Aljonova Nargiza Rashidjon qizi	
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF CREDIT INTEREST RATES.....	1034
Abdullayev Shakhobiddin Shamsiddinovich	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGIDA LOGISTIKA XARAJATLARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH METODLARI VA SAMARALI TA‘MINOT ZANJIRI MODELI	1037
Safarov Xusan Samandar o‘g‘li, Olimova Bahora Shuxratovna	
INNOVASION IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHATLARI.....	1042
Abdulxakimov Zuxrali Tursunaliyevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA DEPOZIT BAZASI BARQARORLIGIGA TA’SIR ETUVCHI OMIL SIFATIDA FOIZ SIYOSATI VA UNING AMALIY JIHATLARI.....	1047
Axmedova Dilafro‘z Elshodovna	
B2BDA RAQAMLI MARKETINGDAN FOYDALANISH BO‘YICHA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR.....	1053
Abdubotirova Madinaxon	
ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ МЕХАНИЗМ ИННОВАЦИОННО - ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ОТРАСЛИ	1059
Баходирова Хилола Баходировна	
RAQOBATBARDOSH MAHSULOT ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	1063
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna, Abdurazakova Diyora	
ENERGIYA XARAJATLARINI KAMAYTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARASI	1070
Urmanbekova Iroda Farxodovna	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF REMOTE BANKING SERVICES IN THE CONTEXT OF BANKING TRANSFORMATION	1075
Jabborov Bahriddin Rashidovich	

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF REMOTE BANKING SERVICES IN THE CONTEXT OF BANKING TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract. In this article, the scientific and theoretical views on the importance of remote banking services in banking activities, the channels for providing them, and the possibilities for their further expansion were studied. The state of development of remote banking services in the practice of commercial banks of Uzbekistan was analyzed based on collected statistical data.

Key words: remote banking services, internet banking, mobile banking, Bank–Client, online banking.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada masofaviy bank xizmatlarining bank faoliyatidagi ahamiyati, ularni ko'rsatish kanallari va bu xizmatlarni yanada kengaytirish imkoniyatlariga oid ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar o'rganib chiqildi. O'zbekiston tijorat banklari amaliyotida masofaviy bank xizmatlarining rivojlanish holati to'plangan statistik ma'lumotlar asosida tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: masofaviy bank xizmatlari, internet-banking, mobil-banking, Bank–mijoz, onlayn-banking.

Аннотация. В статье исследуются научные взгляды на важность дистанционного банковского обслуживания в банковской сфере, способы их предоставления и возможности для дальнейшего расширения. Практика дистанционного банковского обслуживания в Узбекистане проанализирована на основе собранных статистических данных.

Ключевые слова: удаленное банковское обслуживание, интернет-банкинг, мобильный банкинг, банк-клиент, онлайн-банкинг.

INTRODUCTION

The most effective way to ensure the competitiveness of commercial banks is, first and foremost, to strengthen customers' trust in the banking system, create all necessary conveniences for them, and continuously improve the range, quality, and efficiency of banking services. Today, the intensification of competition in the financial market and the growing demands and expectations of customers require banks not to limit themselves to traditional service delivery models, but to introduce modern banking products and digital solutions. Therefore, commercial banks are increasingly feeling the need to utilize innovative technologies and widely implement remote and digital banking services in order to maintain and enhance their competitiveness.

This issue has also been receiving constant attention from the country's leadership. In particular, in his speeches and Addresses to the Oliy Majlis in recent years, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, has repeatedly emphasized the necessity of deep reforms in the banking and financial system and its transformation in line with modern requirements. Specifically, the Head of State has noted that developing the banking system, strengthening banks' capital and resource base, increasing their profitability, and elevating the quality of customer service to a new level through the wide adoption of digital technologies constitute priority tasks. In this regard, the implementation of comprehensive transformation programs in each commercial bank, as well as the introduction of modern management mechanisms and digital solutions, is being supported at the level of state policy [1].

In order to achieve the above-mentioned objectives, a number of regulatory and legal acts aimed at liberalizing the banking system, creating a healthy competitive environment, and increasing the accessibility of banking services have been adopted in recent years. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3620 dated March 23, 2018, "On Additional Measures to Increase the Accessibility of Banking Services," identified existing problems in the provision of banking services and defined specific tasks to be carried out by banks [2].

This resolution sets out important tasks for the development of cashless payments through the introduction of innovative banking products, including contactless payments, and the wide use of mobile and digital technologies; the active implementation of these technologies, especially in social and household services, transport, trade, and public catering sectors, as well as in regional areas; and the expansion of cooperation with international payment systems. All of this contributes to enhancing the competitiveness of commercial banks, ensuring convenient and efficient customer service, and strengthening the position of the national banking system in the international financial market.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

A number of scholarly studies related to the topic were closely examined. These works analyzed researchers' views on remote banking services. In particular, according to the Russian economist V. K. Spilnichenko, "remote servicing of a bank account represents a set of information services and the execution of operations on a client's account based on instructions given without visiting the bank. The remote bank account servicing system is based on the client's access to the bank's database through a telecommunications system" [3].

N. I. Likhodeeva, in turn, defines the remote bank account servicing system as a technology for providing banking services based on orders submitted remotely by the client, using computer technologies, without visiting the bank [4].

K. A. Zabrodiskaya and A. O. Zakharova describe remote banking services as "the activity of a bank aimed at creating optimal conditions for its clients through remote servicing of bank accounts" [5].

Summarizing the above viewpoints, remote bank account servicing systems can be defined as technologies for providing banking services based on instructions submitted by clients remotely, that is, without visiting the bank.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In conducting the research, interviews were held with scholars and industry practitioners involved in the development of remote services in commercial banks. Their written and oral opinions were analyzed, expert evaluation methods were applied, processes were observed, and a systemic approach to economic phenomena and processes was employed. In addition, comparative analysis based on the author's own practical experience was carried out, which enabled the formulation of relevant conclusions, proposals, and recommendations in the studied areas.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In recent years, banks have been offering various innovative banking services in order to improve the quality of customer service and enhance the range and standard of services provided. Remote banking services represent a complex of services that enable the execution of various banking operations remotely. For this purpose, it is sufficient to use a computer or a mobile phone without visiting a banking institution.

Remote technologies provide customers with maximum convenience in accessing banking services and allow them to minimize time and financial costs in the process of interacting with the bank.

Depending on the nature of the services provided to customers, remote service systems are divided into two types:

- informational;
- transactional.

Informational banking is aimed at providing customers with financial information, whereas transactional banking enables the execution of financial operations.

The main principle of remote banking services is the remote exchange of various types of information between the customer and the bank. In this process, the bank ensures the security of the relevant operations.

The types of remote bank account servicing systems include the following.

Bank–Client is a computer-based system in which special software is installed on the customer's computer. This software stores all customer data on the computer, primarily payment documents and account statements. Direct communication between the bank and the customer's computer is carried out via a modem.

Internet banking is a system that allows customers to manage their deposit accounts, including accounts opened for bank cards, via the internet. This type of service is designed to enable customers to make payments in real time while being remotely connected to the bank. Users access the system through a web browser. The internet banking system is hosted on the bank's web server. Through the bank's website, users can view all their data, including payment documents and account statements.

Through internet banking services, customers, at their workplace or in any other convenient location, can at any time:

- make payments;
- monitor the stages of payment execution;
- obtain all relevant reports.

Using internet banking, customers can connect to the bank's website via the internet from their workplace, monitor funds credited to their accounts, and prepare and submit money transfers to the bank.

The mobile banking system is developed on the basis of internet banking technology.

SMS banking is a system that enables bank customers to receive information in the form of SMS messages about transactions on their deposit accounts and accounts opened for bank cards. To obtain account information, the customer must send a designated SMS request to the bank's special phone number.

For customers, the SMS banking service provides the ability to obtain prompt information on the following:

- funds credited to the account;
- expenditures made from the account;
- account balance;
- banking operations carried out during the day (figure 1).

Figure 1. Number of users of remote banking service systems as of January 1 [6]

As can be seen from the data presented in the above figure, the number of users of this system has increased significantly over the past decade.

With regard to the evolution of this system, the Unified National Processing Center and the CLICK company can be identified as the initiators of remote banking services [7].

Starting from September 1, 2013, the joint UZCARD–CLICK project implemented between the Unified National Processing Center and the CLICK company became one of the key milestones in the digitalization of payment systems in Uzbekistan. Within the framework of this project, users of all UZCARD online plastic cards issued by any commercial bank operating in the country were given the opportunity to connect the UZCARD SMS notification service to their mobile phones via any bank branch or infokiosk. Subsequently, the possibility was introduced to link a plastic card to the system by sending a free USD request from the connected mobile phone. As a result, users were provided with the ability to make payments via their mobile phones.

The main distinguishing feature of this project was that all payment transactions were carried out without intermediary fees, that is, without additional commissions. This significantly increased the accessibility and convenience of financial services for the population and business entities. Overall, the introduction of innovative services for online plastic card users became an important factor in increasing the share of cashless transactions, enhancing transparency in monetary circulation, and strengthening trust in the banking system in the country.

As of 2025, the reforms initiated in this area have been further deepened, and mobile banking services offered by commercial banks have evolved into a comprehensive ecosystem that fully covers the daily financial needs of the population. Today, individuals can use commercial banks' mobile applications to carry out real-time card-to-card (P2P) transfers, make tax and budget payments, pay for utilities, communication services, education, and other mandatory and voluntary payments. In addition, the practice of obtaining microloans and consumer loans online, repaying loans remotely, opening online deposits, and opening deposit and loan (credit) accounts without visiting a bank has become widespread.

Furthermore, opportunities to make payments using international bank cards, perform online currency conversion, manage foreign currency accounts, and use payment services integrated with e-commerce platforms have expanded significantly. This contributes to improving digital financial literacy among the population, saving time and financial resources, and eliminating regional limitations in access to banking services.

At the same time, the digitalization of banking services for enterprises and organizations has also entered a new stage. As of 2025, through remote bank account management systems, legal entities are able to manage account funds in real time, conduct settlements with counterparties, and prepare electronic payment documents. In addition, the practice of remotely submitting electronic applications to servicing banks for the purchase and conversion of foreign currency, as well as electronic payroll and equivalent payment statements, has been widely implemented.

Overall, the processes of introducing digital payment services that began with the UZCARD-CLICK joint project have, by 2025, become a key factor in ensuring the stability, competitiveness, and innovative development of the country's banking system. These processes contribute to the formation of a cashless economy, the reduction of the shadow economy, and the elevation of the quality of banking services provided to the population and business entities to a new level.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

As a result of the analysis conducted on the prospects for the development of remote banking services in Uzbekistan, the following proposals and recommendations have been formulated.

1. In order to develop remote banking services and improve remote customer service systems, each commercial bank should develop its own dedicated strategic program. This program should define a clear roadmap for the gradual transition of all banking services to remote and online formats. The roadmap must clearly specify sources of financing, implementation timelines, responsible structural units, and the launch dates of relevant projects.

2. At present, the range of services provided remotely by commercial banks includes utility and other mandatory payments, card-to-card money transfers, online currency conversion, online deposit services, as well as retail lending services offered by certain banks. At the next stage, it is advisable to expand the scope of these services. In particular, this includes creating opportunities for sending and receiving funds abroad through integration with international money transfer systems, as well as introducing virtual issuance services for plastic cards.

The development of remote banking services naturally increases the need for customer identification. Therefore, in cases where remote identification by bank staff is required when providing services through mobile banking platforms, it is advisable to create mechanisms for integration with the databases of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in order to ensure reliable and secure customer identification.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 12

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
